

MESO-SCALE MODELLING IN THERMOPLASTIC 5-HARNESS SATIN WEAVE COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

In this paper, meso-scale modeling of a satin weave composite is presented. Numerical results such as local strain variation and local damage initiation are validated using strain mapping and acoustic emission techniques. To validate the sequence of damage initiation and their locations in different layers of the laminate, microscopic analysis is conducted on tensile test specimens.

Keywords: Textile composite, finite element analysis (FEA), periodic boundary conditions (PBC), Meso-scale, acoustic emission (AE)

INTRODUCTION

The analysis of local structural behaviour of the textile composites is difficult, due to the complex weaving pattern of the yarns. The periodicity of the textile reinforcement enables us to evaluate the macro mechanical properties of the composite by using micro mechanical methods, which provides the overall behaviour of the composite from the known properties of the reinforcing phase and matrix phase through the analysis of a Representative Volume Element (RVE).

Unlike the estimation of elastic constants using unit cell FE analysis, the procedure for stress and damage analysis of unit cell is not firmly established. In the regard of stress and damage analysis of unit cell, Zako [1, 2] studied the effect of local yarn parameters such as, yarn flattening ratio (width to thickness), and yarn volume fraction on the damage initiation and strength properties of the unit cell. The above research work concludes that in the elastic region, internal yarn nesting of the laminate does not show considerable effect on the stress vs. strain curve. Once damage occurs in the unit cell, the local parameters show considerable effect on stress vs. strain behaviour.

Current research work is intended to study the local behaviour of thermo plastic 5-harness satin weave composite, by using the full-field strain measurements and layer wise damage analysis. In order to achieve the better agreement between numerical and experimental results, more attention is devoted to study the effect of unit cell stacking and boundary conditions on the local strain and damage behaviour of the unit cell.

ESTIMATION OF ELASTIC CONSTANTS

The textile properties of the above mentioned satin weave geometry is measured using micro-ct technique at 20 different locations of the unit cell. And the averaged values are listed in the Table1. The above mentioned composite has T300JB carbon fibres as a reinforcement and PPS (PolyPhenylene Sulfide) as a matrix (Table 2), with 50:50 weight ratios in both warp and weft directions.

Table 1. Geometrical properties of textile reinforcement

Textile properties		Yarn properties	
<i>Weave pattern</i>	5 Harness satin weave	<i>Width of yarns, mm</i>	1.32
<i>Spacing between yarns, mm</i>	1.48	<i>Thickness of yarns, mm</i>	0.156
<i>Ply thickness, mm</i>	0.312	<i>Fibre volume fraction in yarns, %</i>	70
<i>Unit cell width, mm</i>	7.42	<i>Number of fibres per tow, K</i>	3000
<i>Fibre diameter, μm</i>	7	<i>Fibre volume fraction at unit cell level, %</i>	50

By using the above mentioned textile properties, construction of the unit cell geometrical model and the FE mesh to the unit cell is accomplished using ‘WiseTex, and ‘MeshTex’ software’s respectively[3]. The local yarn volume fraction obtained from the ‘WiseTex’ is 70%. By using this local yarn volume fraction, micro level material properties of the impregnated yarns are calculated using analytical Chamis formulations, and assigned to the yarn cross sections in their local coordinate system. The volume fraction of fibres obtained from the ‘WiseTex’ at the unit cell level is 49.8%, which is in the limits of supplier data (51.5% measured). In order to evaluate the elastic constant of the meso volume, periodic boundary conditions and the volume averaging technique is applied to the unit cell as explained by Lomov et al [4]. The obtained numerical elastic constants are compared with the experimental results as shown in the Table 2.

Table 2. Elastic constants of fibre, matrix, carbon-pps UD and textile

Young moduli, <i>GPa</i>		Shear moduli, <i>GPa</i>		Poisson’s ratio	
Carbon fibres[4, 5]; (coordinate "1" – is the fibre direction)					
<i>E1</i> ,	231.00	<i>G23</i>	10.7	ν_{23}	0.3
<i>E2= E3</i>	28.00	<i>G12= G13</i>	24.00	$\nu_{12}= \nu_{13}$	0.26
PPS matrix (CETEX PPS BRYTE technologies technical data sheet)					
<i>E</i>	3.80	<i>G</i>	1.38	ν	0.37
Unidirectional composite (Chamis model)					
<i>E1</i>	162.60	<i>G23</i>	5.07	ν_{23}	0.35
<i>E2= E3</i>	13.70	<i>G12= G13</i>	6.50	$\nu_{12}= \nu_{13}$	0.29
Homogenized elastic constants of the unit cell					
<i>E1</i>	56.49	<i>G23</i>	3.48	ν_{23}	0.41
<i>E2</i>	56.49	<i>G12</i>	4.28	ν_{12}	0.08
Experimental elastic constants					
<i>E1</i>	57	<i>G23</i>	-NA-	ν_{23}	-NA-
<i>E2</i>	57	<i>G12</i>	4.17	ν_{12}	0.05

FULL-FIELD STRAIN MEASUREMENTS

Detailed analysis of local mechanical behavior in the textile composites is fundamental for understanding their mechanics and validating sophisticated computational models. The digital image correlation technique (LIMESS) is applied to the full-field strain determination[6] in thermo-plastic 5-harness satin weave composite under tensile loading. The LIMESS results are used to assess and improve the computational results.

In order to validate the computational local strain values, the unit cell FE analysis is started with the conventional 3D PBC on the assumption that the unit cell is chosen from the middle of the laminate. In this case, comparison of local FE strains with the LIMESS strain measurements would be misleading, because LIMESS strain measurements were obtained from the surface of the laminate. To get an insight into the variation of local strain between the surface (experiment) and inner layer of the laminate (simulation), the results are compared and shown in the Figure 1.

For 1.1% of applied global strain (Fig 1a), there is a good correlation in the local strain values between FE and LIMESS results (Figure 1d). Where as, qualitatively there is a difference in the occurrence of maximum strain location. In FE analysis, the maximum strain occurs at the edge of the weft yarn, perpendicular to the loading direction (Fig 1a). In contrast, the maximum local strain in the experiment occurs on the centre of the weft yarn (Fig 1b).

Figure 1. Local strain analysis

In the above case, the reason for the qualitative difference in strain location is due to the 3D PBC, which restricts the out-of-plane deformation of the unit cell (Z-direction).

The next step in the full field strain analysis will be validating the local strain variation on the surface of the unit cell. In order to simulate this, single unit cell FE analysis with 3D pbc is changed to the FE analysis four periodically stacked unit cell (Figure 1c) from the laminate of eight layers. And the boundary conditions were chosen such a way that, one of the yz surfaces is restrained in the x direction and the tensile displacement is applied on the opposite face of yz surface. The periodic boundary conditions are applied to both zx surfaces. Finally, z-symmetry applied is to the bottom xy surface and top xy surface is free.

With the above loading conditions, the qualitative comparison of local strain locations between the experiment and FE simulations shows good correlation (Figure 1b, c). The maximum strain in both experiment and simulation occurs at the centre of the weft yarn. For the quantitative assessment, the local strain comparison at the yarn cross over position (Figure 1d), the maximum strain obtained from the FE simulation and experiment are 1.7% and 1.45% respectively (strain profile along black arrow in the Figure 1 (b) (c)) for the applied global strain of 1.1% in X-direction.

The reason for the difference in the local strain values between the experiment and simulation is explained by Ivanov et al[7]. In which the author explained the difference in local strain values between the periodically stacked unit cell and the unit cell stacked with nested configuration (closer to the original composite weave pattern) for a twill weave composite. The above mentioned research work concludes that the local strain values in the shifted yarn configuration predicts less strain compared to the periodic yarn configuration.

LOCAL DAMAGE ANALYSIS

In the process of understanding the local structural behavior of textile composites, local damage is another important parameter. Homogeneous engineering materials subjected to external loads usually fail as a result of critical crack propagation. Advanced fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) composites, in contrast, exhibit gradual damage accumulation to failure. Damage development in composites starts early in the loading process due to the inherent inhomogeneity of these materials. Advanced composite materials consist of reinforcing fibres, embedded in a matrix. These reinforcing elements are stiff and strong, and often exhibit substantial anisotropy of mechanical properties. The matrix material, on the other hand, is usually soft and isotropic. An external load applied to such a structure results in severely inhomogeneous stress and strain fields. Early damage starts to develop in the micro volumes within the composite in which the localized stress reached to the strength or fracture limit of a particular constituent or an interface between the constituents. The resulting crack sizes correlate with the sizes of material inhomogeneities responsible for stress inhomogeneity. The micro cracks that develop are usually too small to cause final failure of the composite. A substantial number of these micro cracks accumulate in the composite before final failure[8].

For the FE analysis of damage in unit cell the following approach is employed. Initially, the occurrence of damage is detected by using Hoffmann failure criteria. However, this criterion cannot indicate the type of damage mode of the fibres, where the architecture of

the fibre arrangement plays an important role. These modes of the damage can be classified into four modes[4]. The mode L represents the fibre breaking, the T, Z represent the transverse and shear cracking. By calculating the corresponding stress-to-strength ratios for the different modes, we consider that the damage mode that is taking place is the one whose stress-to-strength ratio has the maximum value. On the other hand, in order to characterize each one of the damage modes, we refer to the use of Murakami's damage tensor [4, 9], which is coupled with the stress-strain tensor.

To start the damage analysis of the unit cell, in a similar fashion of the elastic analysis, the micromechanical strength properties of carbon and PPS (Table 3) are homogenized with Chamis [10] analytical strength homogenization formulas. These homogenized strength material properties are assigned to the yarn cross sections along with the elastic material properties. Finally, the above mentioned anisotropic Murakami damage model has been implemented in to the ABAQUS software. This enables us to simulate the damage in unit cell

The main motive behind of the unit cell damage analysis is twofold, namely:

- (1) Finding the FE damage initiation strain, this can be verified with the experimental AE (Acoustic Emission) technique.
- (2) Finding the FE damage initiation location in the unit cell, this can be verified with the microscopically observed damage initiation location on the quasi-static tensile test on the composite specimen.

As explained in the full-field strain analysis, the damage analysis of the unit cell is started with 3D pbc. At $<0.2\%>$ of global tensile strain in warp yarn direction (Fig. 2 X-direction), the damage initiation in the weft yarn at yarn crossover position is detected by Hofmann criteria. And the direction of the damage is detected by Murakami damage parameters. The relative contribution of each damage mode to the final damage of the local element in the transverse direction (d_T) is listed below at 0.2% of global strain.

$$d_l = 0.98 \quad d_T = 0.78 \quad d_z = 0.98 \quad (3 \text{ normal components})$$

$$d_{LT} = 0.77 \quad d_{ZL} = 0.96 \quad d_{TZ} = 0.77 \quad (3 \text{ shear components})$$

$d = 0.99$ No damage
 $d = 0.01$ Completely damage in that particular mode

Table 3. Micro-mechanical homogenization of strength values

<i>Strength parameter</i>	<i>T300JB carbon fibre</i>	<i>PPS matrix</i>	<i>Impregnated yarn (UD)</i>
<i>Tensile strength, MPa</i>	4210	90.3	$F_L^t = 2947$ $F_T^t = 79.6$ $F_Z^t = 79.6$
<i>Compressive strength, MPa</i>	2616	143	$F_L^c = 1832$ $F_T^c = 130.5$ $F_Z^c = 130.5$
<i>Shear strength, MPa</i>	-	63	$F_{TZ}^s = 56.12$ $F_{ZL}^s = 56.12$ $F_{LT}^s = 56.12$

*Note: T300 JB carbon material strength properties are taken from TORAYCA technical datasheet No: CFA-002
PPS material properties are taken from TECHTRON & RYTRON PPS data sheet*

Predominant damage modes for the satin weave composite obtained from the unit cell FE analysis are d_{TZ} , d_{LT} , d_T , due to the weave architecture.

Figure 2. Damage analysis with 3D PBC

Note: SDV7 in the contour indicate the Hoffmann damage criteria ($SDV7 \geq 1.0$ damage initiation)

The next step in the damage analysis will be simulation of damage on the surface of the unit cell. For this purpose, FE analysis is started with four periodically stacked unit cell from the laminate of 8 layers of the laminate. Boundary conditions applied to the stack as explained in the full-field strain analysis.

During the FE analysis of stacked unit cell, the initial transverse damage is detected by Hoffman criteria at $\langle 0.2\% \rangle$ global tensile strain, on the surface, where Z-symmetry is applied (Fig 4a). The damage initiation strain in the above case is equal to the damage initiation strain obtained from the single unit cell FE analysis with 3D periodic boundary conditions.

By increasing the tensile strain from $\langle 0.2\% \rangle$, without reducing the homogenized elastic constants of the unit cell, the transverse damage is detected by Hoffman criteria on the free surface of the unit cell at $\langle 0.44\% \rangle$ global strain. The location of the damage is shown in Fig 4b.

Figure 4. FE analysis with 4 periodically stacked unit cells

In order to validate the damage initiation strain obtained from FE simulations, experimental acoustic emission technique is conducted as explained in the following section.

VALIDATION OF DAMAGE INITIATION

Modal Acoustic Emission (MAE) technique is suitable for the detection of wide range of micro-structural failures in composite materials, there by validating the FE results. When the failure mechanism is activated, part of total strain energy is dissipated as a wave that propagates from failure source through the medium. In polymer matrix composite three different intra-ply failure modes can be identified, viz. fibre breakage, matrix cracking and fibre matrix debonding.

Once the composite test specimen is mounted on the tensile test machine, two sensors are attached at the ends of the specimen. The distance between the two sensors is 150mm to record acoustic events. The VALLEN AE system was used to record the damage accumulation hits until the load on tensile machine reaches to 30kN. After filtering the end tab noise from the sensor data, stress versus cumulative elastic energy is plotted and shown in the Fig 5a. In a comprehensive way, the plots in Fig 5(a, b) depict the relation between the damage initiation stress and strain. The damage initiation stress is approximately 80MPa, which corresponds to the global tensile strain of <0.18%>.

Figure 5. AE curves

The damage initiation strain obtained from the AE corresponds very well with the FE damage initiation strain obtained from the single unit cell with 3D pbc. AE technique presented in this section is to get the damage initiation strain quantitatively. It can not give any indication of the damage location. In order to validate the FE damage locations, microscopic analysis is conducted on the composite specimens as explained in the following section.

VALIDATION OF DAMAGE LOCATION

Microscopic analysis of the composite specimens is the possible technique for evaluating the damage initiation and propagation at different locations of the laminate. The technique presented here is based on capturing and performing qualitative analysis of microscopic images of the 5-harness satin weave composite.

Quasi static tensile tests were performed on the polished composite laminate to allow for microscopic inspection of the damage at each and every load increment until the tensile stress reaches to the final failure (750 MPa). The damage developed in the 5-harness satin weave under the static loading takes the form of weft yarn cracking, which is perpendicular to the loading direction. The damage is developed at the yarn crossover positions, and then propagates into the matrix. For one complete unit cell, the observed microscopic damage is shown in the Fig 5.

Figure 5. Microscopic damage analysis on polished edge

The location of crack in weft yarn changes according to the position in the laminate where it occurs. From the damage analysis of microscopic pictures, the entire damage in the satin weave can be divided in to four major locations. Initially, the damage occurs inside the laminate at a stress level between 100-300MPa. The location of the damage is shown in Fig 6a.

By increasing the stress level from 300-400MPa, the damage is observed at the nested yarn location as shown in Fig 6b.

a) Damage location 1

b) Damage at nested yarn configuration

Figure 6. Damage analysis inside the laminate

The next damage is observed on the free surface of the laminate between the stress levels of 400-500 MPa, where there is no restriction for the out-of-plane deformation. More than 80% of microscopic pictures on the surface of the laminate show damage at the centre of the weft yarn (Fig.7a). The damage locations obtained from microscopic analysis are compared with FE damage locations as well as existing literature shows very good correlation as shown in the Fig 7(b, c). For quantitative comparison, the damage initiation strain obtained from the simulation on the surface of the laminate is 0.44% (Fig4b) (Periodic stacking of unit cells).

And the damage initiation strain from the microscopic analysis varies between 0.6 - 0.75% (nested configuration). The difference in damage initiation strain between the experiment and simulation is almost equal to the strain difference obtained from the full-filled strain measurements on the surface of the laminate (section2).

a) Microscopic damage analysis on the surface of the laminate

b) Transverse damage on the free surface at 0.44% of strain (2D PBC with Z-symmetry)

c) Transverse damage on plain weave unit cell with 2D PBC [9]

Figure 7. FE damage location on the surface of the unit cell

Note: SDV2 in the contour indicate the transverse damage

Final damage is observed at the stress levels of 500-700MPa, on edges of the weft yarn where it is tightly packed by load carrying warp yarns as shown in the Fig 8. Both the load carrying warp yarns acts as perfect 3D pbc, and stress concentration at the edges of the weft yarn causes the damage at the edges.

Figure 8. Damage at the edges of the weft yarn

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In order to understand the local mechanical behavior of satin weave composite, a comprehensive study is conducted with the help of experimental and numerical techniques. From the above results, it is evident that there is no effect of internal yarn nesting on the homogenized elastic constants of the unit cell. From the full-field strain measurements, the maximum local strain occurs at the yarn cross over positions. Moreover, the stacking of unit cells and the boundary conditions applied to the unit cell can alter the local strain and damage profiles both qualitatively as well as quantitatively at yarn crossover positions. But at the flat yarn positions, LIMESS local strain values corresponds very well with the FE results (single, unit cell stack).

The microscopic damage analysis as well as the acoustic emission technique predicts the occurrence of the damage in satin weave around 80 MPa or 0.2% global applied strain. The damage in the satin weave composite takes the form of weft yarn cracking at the yarn crossover positions. More over, there is a similarity between the damage locations as well as the maximum strain locations. Symmetry boundary conditions applied at the bottom of unit cell stack, and the periodic stacking of the unit cells increases the out-of-plane deformation and cause increased local strain and early damage at yarn crossover position. The future research work in this area will be shifting the unit cells (on going) according to the real composite weave architecture, so that the difference between the computational and experimental results can be reduced.

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